

A Bibliometric Analysis of Senior Tourism: Trends, Insights, and Future Directions

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Keywords: Senior Tourism, Retirement Tourism, Third Age Tourism, Bibliometric, Bibliometrix, Biblioshiny.

JEL Codes:
I11, L83,
Z32

Abstract

The senior tourism sector, akin to other industries, has continued to diversify and expand. Among these emerging sectors, senior tourism has become one of the most prominent. This study aims to analyze research conducted in the field of senior tourism from 2014 to 2024 and identify potential future opportunities. To this end, articles published in English in the topic category (title, abstract, keyword plus, and author keywords) on Web of Science, containing the terms ‘senior tourism,’ ‘retirement tourism,’ ‘senior friendly tourism,’ ‘third age tourism,’ ‘elderly tourism,’ and ‘elderly tour,’ were examined, resulting in a total of 388 articles. The results indicate that although publications related to senior tourism have increased, the number of citations has declined. The country with the highest citation count is China, and the most relevant affiliation is Hong Kong Polytechnic University. Among the 15 most frequently occurring keywords, terms such as hospitality, sustainability, motivation(s), travel, rural tourism, well-being, and quality of life are particularly prominent. Additionally, it was observed that single-authored papers are more prevalent than multi-authored works. The senior tourism literature, between 2014 and 2024, has transitioned from sector-specific and rural tourism topics to innovative themes such as individual well-being, health, and sustainability. As of 2024, strategic issues such as corporate social responsibility, gender differences, and competitive advantage have become more prominent. Senior tourism offers significant opportunities for the sustainable growth of the health tourism industry, in response to demographic shifts and the increasing travel demands of the aging population.

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1.Introduction

Health tourism, which includes medical tourism and is not limited to international tourism (L. Jiang et al., 2022: 1) constitutes 14% of the total global tourism revenue, a figure generally associated with the SPA industry (Dunets et al., 2020: 2214), and is defined as all relationships and developments arising from the stays and travels of individuals whose primary motivation and objective are to improve or maintain their health, or to recover from illnesses (Białk-Wolf, 2010; Roman et al., 2023: 11).

Older individuals play a significant role in contemporary leisure mobility, bringing their pursuit of health, social status, and freedom to the forefront of their vacation and travel choices. This group, which freely spends its savings during retirement, continues to challenge age-related stereotypes in their pursuit of well-being and happiness (Stončikaitė, 2022: 335). In this context, socio-demographic characteristics, leisure activities, and successful aging are key determinants of the quality of life for older individuals, playing an important role in their holiday and travel preferences (Demir et al., 2024: 252). The increasing global aging trend and the diversification of retirement models have made senior tourism a significant retirement model for older individuals (Zhang et al., 2023). Older individuals from the Baby Boomer generation play a key role in global leisure mobility, promoting productivity, self-management, and savings. "Third age golden" consumers are encouraged to travel to express their health, social status, and retirement rewards, spending their savings freely. Many travel abroad to reconnect with their youth, experience well-being, and challenge age-related stereotypes (Stončikaitė, 2022: 343). Chivers (2021) emphasizes the need to approach aging from a new perspective, highlighting the importance of changing fundamental approaches to the aging population. New policies and practices that acknowledge the diversity and uniqueness of the aging experience can contribute to a healthier and more fulfilling aging process (Chivers, 2021: 8). In this context, the positive impacts of tourism on older individuals should not be overlooked. Tourism, by providing both physical and mental satisfaction, supports longevity and health, while effectively enhancing the quality of life for older adults (L. Y. Jiang, 2011).

Bibliometric refers to a range of techniques used for the quantitative analysis of academic literature and scholarly communications, often utilizing web-based citation databases such as Scopus and the Web of Science (Das, 2015; Ghanbari Baghestan et al., 2019: 2). In senior tourism research, bibliometric analysis is essential for identifying trends, key contributors, and research gaps, providing a comprehensive understanding of the field's development. Bibliometric studies on health tourism and its subfield, medical tourism, reveal academic

trends and research topics in this area. A study examining 1,535 documents indexed in Scopus between 1952 and 2020 emphasizes the need to consider both cognitive factors and emotional experiences in medical tourism (Habibi et al., 2022: 415). Similarly, research analyzing 459 articles from Scopus between 1987 and 2020 highlights that medical tourism primarily focuses on areas such as organization, marketing, and healthcare services (Campra et al., 2022: 184). Another study, reviewing 3,130 publications in Scopus, identifies healthcare quality, destination image, and tourist satisfaction as key themes in medical tourism (Dhakate et al., 2023: 902). A study evaluating 3,397 documents indexed in Scopus between 1963 and 2024 suggests that health tourism has shown an increase since 2009, with technology playing a role in enhancing experiences in this field (Lukose et al., 2024: 2). A study examining Chinese articles on health tourism published between 1981 and 2021 in China emphasizes the growth of health tourism since 2004 and the significant role of government policies in this development (Sun et al., 2022: 1). Research analyzing 1,224 documents indexed in Web of Science found that policy discussions in medical tourism are limited, and studies focus on specific areas (Virani et al., 2020: 3). A bibliometric analysis of senior tourism, examining 332 English articles in Web of Science between 2019 and 2023, found a lack of collaboration between authors and institutions in this field. This may be due to the impact of COVID-19 on tourism and a shift toward other research areas (Zhao et al., 2023: 211). With the growing elderly population, this demographic group is increasingly affected by adverse economic and social conditions. Travel is one of the effective ways to mitigate these impacts and can have a positive effect on the quality of life of older individuals (Alén et al., 2017: 1464).

Identifying the trends in studies on senior tourism over the years is of great importance in understanding how academic interest in this field has evolved, which topics have gained prominence, and which research areas may hold potential for the future. Such an analysis can provide a more comprehensive perspective on the travel preferences, motivations, and challenges faced by the elderly population, contributing to the development of strategic planning in the tourism sector. Additionally, it can provide valuable data on how tourism businesses should adapt their services to improve the travel experiences of older individuals.

The primary objective of this study is to raise awareness of senior tourism and contribute to the academic and sectoral developments in this field. As the elderly population grows, the increasing significance of this area in the tourism sector makes its study vital not only for determining the direction of academic research but also for guiding industry practices. In this context, the study focuses on three main areas:

1. Determining the productivity and citation levels of studies on senior tourism: Evaluating the change in interest towards senior tourism in the academic literature over time will help identify the most cited and influential research in this field. Furthermore, identifying the scholars interested in senior tourism, the academic journals publishing the most papers, and the countries contributing the most to the field will allow for a comprehensive analysis of the current state of the area.
2. Identifying the relationships between key terms used in the studies: To understand the primary themes around which research on senior tourism has been shaped, the connections between key terms will be analyzed. This analysis will help identify the fundamental concepts related to senior tourism, reveal the interdisciplinary dimensions of the subject, and provide a better understanding of the relationships between different research areas. Thus, it will highlight the academic disciplines intersecting with senior tourism and identify the factors that have directed the development of this field.
3. Analyzing the change in key terms over time to identify trends: To identify which topics have emerged over time and which research areas have gained momentum in senior tourism, keyword trends will be analyzed over the years. This analysis will explore which topics became popular in specific periods, which trends have strengthened over time, and which have lost significance, offering predictions about which areas may see increased research in the future.

This study aims to present an overarching framework for research in senior tourism, providing guiding insights both for the academic world and for practitioners in the tourism sector. It also offers a comprehensive perspective on how sectoral practices can be shaped to enhance the travel experiences of older individuals.

2. Methodology

The study was conducted using the `biblioshiny()` command in the `bibliometrix` package within The R Project for Statistical Computing infrastructure (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). The data were exported in the `bib` format. A total of 388 articles retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) were analyzed in detail using the topics: ‘senior tourism’, ‘senior friendly tourism’, ‘retirement tourism’, ‘third age tourism’, ‘elderly tourism’, and ‘elderly tour’. Visualization of the data was done using the built-in visualization tools within the software. The study aimed to cover the complete last decade and current status, analyzing the period between 2014 and 2024.

The search criteria in Web of Science (WoS) were formulated as: “Topic= senior tourism, or Topic= senior friendly tourism, or Topic= retirement tourism, or Topic= third age tourism, or Topic= elderly tourism, or Topic= elderly tour.”

The data were analyzed under several categories, including: 1) Main Information, 2) Annual Scientific Production, 3) Average Citations Per Year, 4) Most Relevant Sources, 5) Most Relevant Authors, 6) Most Relevant Affiliations, 7) Corresponding Author's Countries, 8) Most Frequent Words, 9) WordCloud, 10) TreeMap, 11) Trend Topics, 12) Co-occurrence Network, 13) Thematic Map, and 14) Thematic Evolution.

Descriptive bibliometric analysis

Table 1. Main information

Description	Results
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2014:2024
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	388
Documents	816
Annual Growth Rate %	11.9
Document Average Age	3.94
Average citations per doc	15.44
References	39331
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)*	1531
Author's Keywords (DE)	3118
AUTHORS	
Authors	2426
Authors of single-authored docs	120
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	123
Co-Authors per Doc	3.32
International co-authorships %	29.53

DOCUMENT TYPES

article	758
article; book chapter	18
article; early access	33
article; proceedings paper	6
article; retracted publication	1

*KeyWords Plus refers to words or phrases that frequently appear in the titles of a paper's references but do not appear in the title of the paper itself.

Table 1 provides an overview of the general status of academic works spanning the years 2014-2024. Of the 816 documents, 388 are articles, with an annual growth rate of 11.9%, indicating a consistent increase in academic production. The average age of the documents is 3.94 years, suggesting a relatively recent body of work, while the average number of citations per document is 15.44, reflecting a substantial impact within the academic community. The total number of references utilized across these works amounts to 39,331, signaling a broad engagement with existing literature.

In terms of content, the studies feature 3,118 unique keywords and 1,531 Keywords Plus (a term used to describe words or phrases frequently found in the titles of cited references but not in the article title itself), which demonstrates the diversity of topics addressed and the wide-ranging nature of the research. The contributions come from 2,426 authors, highlighting the collaborative nature of these works. The average number of authors per document is 3.32, and the international collaboration rate stands at 29.53%, indicating that these studies have been conducted on a global scale and have garnered international attention. Nonetheless, a total of 123 single-authored articles, comprising 388 articles in total, indicate that a portion of the works have been produced by individual researchers.

In terms of document types, 758 articles, 18 book chapters, 33 early access articles, and 6 conference papers are identified. Notably, there is a single retracted publication.

Article and Author Data

This section presents the data related to the articles and authors in the form of figures and accompanying explanations.

Figure 1. Annual scientific production

Figure 1 illustrates the annual scientific production from 2014 to 2024. The graph reveals a consistent upward trend in scientific output, with a notable increase observed particularly after 2018. During the period from 2014 to 2016, there was a steady rise in production, followed by a decline between 2017 and 2018. Starting from 2019, a rapid growth trend is evident, continuing until 2024. Scientific production, which began with approximately 40 articles in 2014, approaches 120 articles by 2024. This indicates a nearly threefold increase in article production over the course of the 10-year period.

Figure 2. Average citations per year

Figure 2 shows the changes in the annual average citation count between 2014 and 2024. It can be observed that there is a fluctuating pattern in the annual average citations. The year 2020 stands out as the year with the highest average citation count. In contrast, lower citation levels

were recorded in 2014 and 2018. Since 2021, there has been a rapid decline in the average citation count, with this value reaching a significantly lower level by 2024. This trend may be linked to the fact that newly published works have not yet received a sufficient number of citations. Additionally, the variation in citation rates could be explained by factors such as the popularity of the topics of the published works or the time elapsed since their publication.

Figure 3. Most relevant sources

Figure 3 illustrates the most relevant sources between 2014 and 2024. During this period, Sustainability has emerged as the most frequently cited journal, with 44 publications. It is followed by Tourism Management, International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality, Current Issues in Tourism, and Annals of Tourism Research, in that order.

Figure 4. Most relevant authors

Figure 4 displays the most relevant authors in the field of senior tourism. The researcher most closely associated with this topic is Kim Myung Ja. Following Kim, the next most relevant authors are Alen Elisa, Balderas-Cejudo Adela, Losada Nieves, and Goh Edmund.

Figure 5. Most relevant affiliations

Figure 5 illustrates the most relevant affiliations in the field of senior tourism. The top five universities are Hong Kong Polytech University (China), University of Aveiro (Portugal), Zhejiang University (China), Kyung Hee University (South Korea), and Sun Yat-sen University (China). It can be observed that the universities are primarily concentrated in Asia, with China placing more emphasis on senior tourism compared to other countries.

Figure 6. Corresponding author's countries

Figure 6 under the title "Corresponding Author's Countries" shows the contributions of authors from different countries to scientific publications. The articles are categorized into Single Country Publications (SCP) and Multiple Country Publications (MCP). China is the leading country with the highest number of publications, predominantly in the SCP format. The United States and the United Kingdom follow China, with a higher proportion of MCP publications. Turkey ranks 12th, with 17 articles in the SCP format and 2 in the MCP format.

Data on Words and Trends

This section presents data related to words and word trends, accompanied by figures and explanations. These analyses aim to identify key concepts in senior tourism research, understand the evolution of the field, and provide insights into potential future research areas. The findings offer a comprehensive overview of the main terms driving scholarly work in this domain.

Figure 7. Most frequent words and wordcloud

Figure 7 displays the Most Frequent Words and WordCloud based on the keywords used in the studies. The Most Frequent Words section includes 10 words, while the WordCloud section features 50 words.

Figure 8. TreeMap

Figure 8 is based on the 50 most frequently used keywords in the studies. When examining both Figure (Most Frequent Words and WordCloud) and Figure (TreeMap), it is observed that the term 'Tourism' encompasses all other themes. Keywords such as 'Senior Tourism,' 'Elderly,' and 'Seniors' highlight the role of older individuals in tourism. 'Covid-19' emphasizes the impact of the pandemic on the tourism sector, while 'Sustainability' addresses issues related to environmental and economic sustainability.

Figure 9. Trend topics

Figure 9 illustrates the frequency and prevalence of trending words over time from 2014 to 2024.

Before the pandemic (2014-2019), the tourism sector primarily focused on traditional themes and demographic changes. During this period, terms such as ‘second home,’ ‘retirees,’ ‘rural tourism,’ ‘senior tourism,’ ‘sustainability,’ and ‘hospitality’ were prominent. With the increasing interest in elderly travelers, themes like ‘senior tourism’ and ‘elderly tourism’ gained significance. Additionally, the rise of rural tourism and sustainability were key topics, indicating a growing emphasis on alternative tourism types aimed at enhancing individual well-being. Alongside traditional themes, forward-looking concepts such as ‘climate change’ and eco-friendly tourism also emerged during this period.

During and after the pandemic (2020-2024), the term ‘Covid-19’ clearly highlights the transformative impact of the pandemic on the tourism industry. This period saw the rise of innovative and digitalization-focused concepts such as ‘smart tourism,’ ‘subjective well-being,’ and ‘grounded theory.’ Smart tourism reflects the integration of digital technologies and data analytics into the tourism sector, while the emphasis on individual well-being and experiences has increased. Furthermore, the restrictions and shifting consumer behaviours induced by the pandemic led to a more flexible and technology-driven tourism approach. ‘Sustainability’ remained a crucial theme in the post-pandemic era, serving as a fundamental element of a resilient tourism model. Additionally, the term ‘intention’ was examined between 2016 and 2023, indicating its relevance over multiple years.

Figure 10. Co-occurrence network

Figure 10 presents the Co-occurrence Network based on the keywords used in the studies. The figure highlights the direct relationship between ‘Senior Tourism’ and the terms ‘motivation’ and ‘travel,’ while ‘tourism’ is closely associated with ‘Covid-19,’ ‘hospitality,’ and ‘senior.’

The direct link between ‘Senior Tourism’ and ‘motivation’ indicates that research has focused on the motivational factors influencing elderly individuals’ travel decisions. This suggests that aspects such as health considerations, the desire for social connections, and cultural experiences play a crucial role in shaping senior tourists' preferences.

The relationship between ‘Senior Tourism’ and ‘travel’ reflects the increasing number of studies aimed at understanding elderly individuals’ travel behaviours, travel frequency, and preferred destinations. This connection also highlights the importance of factors such as mobility needs, transportation accessibility, and safety considerations for senior tourists.

The association between ‘tourism’ and ‘Covid-19’ underscores the significant impact of the pandemic on the tourism sector. Changing travel restrictions, health measures, and the restructuring of tourism practices during the pandemic have contributed to the strengthening of this connection.

The link between ‘tourism’ and ‘hospitality’ emphasizes the interdependence of the tourism and accommodation sectors, which constitute a fundamental part of the industry. Meanwhile, the relationship between ‘tourism’ and ‘senior’ reflects the growing presence of elderly travelers in the tourism market. This connection highlights the increasing share of senior tourists, their specific needs, and their economic contributions to the sector.

Figure 11. Thematic map

Figure 11 illustrates the key trends in elderly tourism research (2014-2024) in both theoretical and practical contexts. By showing how the terms are grouped along the axes of centrality and density, it aids in understanding the status and connections of research areas within tourism. The four distinct regions on the map (Motor, Niche, Emerging/Declining, and Basic Themes) represent the positions of themes within the research field.

Motor Themes (Top Right Corner)

Motor themes are central and well-developed areas within the elderly tourism literature, encompassing topics that shape the research field and occupy a strong position. Themes such as "Lifestyle Migration," "Retirement," "Baby Boomers," "Spain," and "Sustainable Performance" highlight the impact of the elderly population on tourism and the relationship between lifestyle-oriented migration during retirement and tourism. Notably, Spain stands out as a popular destination for elderly tourism. Additionally, themes like "Digital Divide" and "Experience" emphasize how access to technology influences tourism experiences and highlight tourism as a personal and meaningful activity for individuals.

Niche Themes (Top Left Corner)

Niche themes represent topics that appeal to a specific audience, are being developed but are less central, and focus on understanding the environmental impacts of tourism and strategies

to address these effects. Themes such as "Climate Change," "Adaptation," "Qualitative Research," and "New Zealand" concentrate on sustainability issues, emphasizing adaptation processes to climate change and regional studies, with examples like New Zealand. Additionally, it is evident that qualitative research is frequently preferred in these areas.

Basic Themes (Bottom Right Corner)

Basic themes are central topics that represent the core concepts of the tourism sector, yet to be fully developed. Themes such as "Tourism," "Senior Tourism," "Covid-19," "Sustainability," "Hospitality," and "Innovation" are critical elements shaping the sector in the post-pandemic era. Notably, Covid-19 and sustainability draw attention, alongside innovation in the sector, while senior tourism (Senior Tourism) emerges as a rapidly growing area both economically and demographically. Additionally, China's rise as an emerging tourism market and the exploration of tourists' travel motivations are significant focal points in research.

Emerging or Declining Themes (Bottom Left Corner)

This region houses emerging or diminishing themes, reflecting areas with potential for change in research interest. Topics such as "Sustainable Development," "Cruise Tourism," and "Elderly Tourists" show potential for shifts in attention. Sustainable development and cruise tourism are areas that may attract increasing interest in the future, while the specific needs and expectations of elderly tourists offer an important perspective that calls for more in-depth exploration of these topics.

Figure 12. Thematic evolution

Figure 12 examines the Thematic Evolution between 2014-2019, 2020-2023, and 2024 based on key terms. These years were selected to identify the development of elderly tourism research before the pandemic, during the pandemic, and in the present (2024). Between 2014-2019, terms such as 'industry,' 'hospitality,' 'lifestyle migration,' 'tourism industry,' 'elderly tourism,'

and 'rural tourism' were prevalent. In contrast, between 2020-2023, terms like 'tourism,' 'covid-19,' 'sustainability,' 'culture,' 'subjective well-being,' 'age,' and 'life satisfaction' were more prominent. By 2024, terms such as 'senior tourist,' 'gender,' 'corporate social responsibility,' 'hospitality,' 'covid-19 pandemic,' 'subjective well-being,' 'China,' 'competitive advantage,' 'senior tourism,' and 'sustainability' stand out.

The period between 2014-2019 reflects a phase in elderly tourism where the focus was more on industry and rural tourism contexts. The key terms used during this period, such as 'industry,' 'hospitality,' 'lifestyle migration,' 'tourism industry,' 'elderly tourism,' and 'rural tourism,' highlight efforts to define elderly tourism as an industry and emphasize the opportunities in rural areas. The concept of 'lifestyle migration' particularly sparked discussions on the movements of elderly individuals, such as long-term stays or retirement migration to rural areas. During this period, elderly tourism was conceptualized as both an industry and a lifestyle phenomenon, though themes such as sustainability and social responsibility had not yet gained prominence.

Individuals aged 65 and over were the first group to leave social environments during the pandemic, resulting in long periods of isolation at home. While this isolation helped reduce the spread of COVID-19 and mortality rates, it had negative effects on mental health, physical health, and functionality. Changes in dietary habits during the time spent at home could trigger heart failure, while a lack of exercise may lead to muscle weakness and falls (Özpinar et al., 2022). The period between 2020-2023 marked a significant turning point in elderly tourism studies due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The key terms from this period, such as 'tourism,' 'covid-19,' 'sustainability,' 'culture,' 'subjective well-being,' 'age,' and 'life satisfaction,' indicate a focus on the effects of the pandemic on elderly tourists' travel behaviors, health concerns, and individual well-being. During this period, themes such as sustainability discussions and individual happiness emerged, and the cultural dimensions of tourism remained important. Efforts to enhance the well-being of elderly tourists and adapt to the changing travel habits post-pandemic became central to the research.

By 2024, elderly tourism studies will have adopted a more strategic and inclusive approach. Key terms such as 'senior tourist,' 'senior tourism,' 'gender,' 'corporate social responsibility,' 'hospitality,' 'covid-19 pandemic,' 'subjective well-being,' 'China,' 'competitive advantage,' and 'sustainability' indicate that the needs of elderly tourists have been more clearly defined, with businesses striving to gain a competitive advantage in response. The prominence of concepts like social responsibility, sustainability, and gender differences in studies reveals that the humanitarian and societal dimensions of elderly tourism are being explored more broadly.

Furthermore, the emphasis on regional focuses, such as China, suggests efforts to adapt elderly tourism to local dynamics. As a result, elderly tourism has shifted from an individual well-being and health-focused approach to broader themes such as strategic planning and social responsibility.

3. Conclusion and Discussion

The bibliometric analysis conducted on elderly tourism literature covering the years 2014-2024 aims to examine the current state of the field and identify future trends.

Annual scientific production has shown a significant increase since 2020. The pandemic period has heightened interest in elderly tourism, leading to a surge in research during this time. By 2024, it is expected that this production will reach its peak. However, it was also noted that citations to these studies have been on a decline since 2020, with the lowest level observed in 2024. In a study by Zhao et al. (2023), while the increased interest in elderly tourism research was highlighted, it was also pointed out that collaboration among researchers remained weak (Zhao et al., 2023: 223). A bibliometric analysis was applied to studies on elderly tourism from 1998-2017, with a detailed examination conducted using CiteSpace on documents collected from Web of Science and Scopus. The results of this research indicated that the growth in elderly tourism studies was slow in the early years of the examined period (Pestana et al., 2019: 329). However, from 2018 onward, it was observed that these studies gained momentum and increased rapidly.

According to the results of the word analysis, key terms such as "well-being," "health tourism," and "retirement migration" occupy a significant place in the elderly tourism literature. These terms point to research addressing the health-related needs of the elderly, post-retirement migration mobility, and general well-being. This suggests that elderly tourism is being examined not only in relation to healthcare services but also from a broader perspective aimed at improving the quality of life for older individuals. These key terms also indicate the increasing prevalence of a multidisciplinary approach that integrates the study of health, quality of life, and migration processes of elderly individuals. This highlights that elderly tourism is becoming an increasingly complex field, with research deepening in this direction.

The thematic evolution analysis reveals that research in elderly tourism focused more on traditional themes between 2014 and 2019, while post-2020, innovative themes such as digitalization and individual well-being have come to the forefront. This shift highlights the growing need for a more multidisciplinary approach in elderly tourism research, with innovative elements like digitalization driving significant transformation in the field. However,

it also suggests that the lack of collaboration and coordination could limit the effectiveness of this transformation. In this context, stronger collaboration and knowledge sharing could lead to more comprehensive and impactful outcomes. Digitalization is initiating a significant transformation in elderly tourism. Digital tools, such as online reservation systems, digital maps, and mobile applications, are making travel experiences more accessible and secure for elderly tourists. However, differences in digital literacy levels may limit the effectiveness of these processes. Nevertheless, user-friendly technologies and digital support services have the potential to overcome these barriers, improving elderly individuals' travel experiences. Individual well-being is directly linked to the psychological and physiological benefits elderly tourists gain from travel. Travel can help elderly individuals strengthen their social connections, improve their mental health, and increase their physical activity. Additionally, elderly tourism contributes to their overall well-being by reducing social isolation and enhancing their quality of life. A bibliometric study by Habibi et al. (2022) on medical tourism highlights that concepts such as "perceived value" and "destination image" have gained increasing importance in recent years (Habibi et al., 2022: 421). In medical tourism, perceived value refers to the balance between the benefits of healthcare services and the expenses incurred. Tourists care about the treatment process and overall experience; factors such as the quality of healthcare, cost-effectiveness, and infrastructure shape this value. Destinations offering affordable, high-quality healthcare may have a high perceived value. Destination image is shaped by factors like a destination's recognition, healthcare accreditations, and reputation, and influences medical tourists' preferences. Reliability and patient experiences strengthen the destination image, which directly affects tourists' travel decisions. In this context, it can be observed that while elderly tourists benefit from tourism activities that cater to their individual needs and preferences, medical tourists prefer countries with high images and values.

Between 2014 and 2019, elderly tourism primarily focused on topics such as industry, rural tourism, and lifestyle migration, addressing the field from a sectoral perspective. The period from 2020 to 2023, influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasized health concerns, individual well-being, sustainability, and cultural dimensions. By 2024, strategic and societal themes such as social responsibility, gender differences, competitive advantage, and sustainability emerged as dominant topics in elderly tourism research. This thematic evolution illustrates the development of elderly tourism from a sectoral perspective, focused on individual well-being, and then to a broader strategic framework. This shift highlights that

elderly tourism has evolved not only as an economic sector but also as a field with societal and cultural impacts, emphasizing the importance of a more sustainable and inclusive approach.

The elderly tourism literature has undergone significant development between 2014 and 2024. Initially, studies focused on sectoral and rural tourism, while after 2020, due to the impact of the pandemic, themes such as health, individual well-being, and sustainability gained more attention. By 2024, strategic topics such as social responsibility, gender differences, and competitive advantage have emerged, indicating that elderly tourism has evolved into a broader and more strategic framework. This evolution demonstrates that elderly tourism has gone beyond being just a provider of healthcare services and has transformed into a more complex, multidimensional sector. New focal points now require a deeper examination of elderly individuals within societal, cultural, and economic contexts, leading to changes in how stakeholders approach strategic thinking. Such strategic research could shape the future direction of elderly tourism and provide the sector with opportunities for more sustainable growth.

Declaration of Research and Publication Ethics

This study does not require ethics committee approval and/or legal/private authorization is compatible with research and publication ethics.

Researcher's Contribution Rate Declaration

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article.

Researcher's Conflict of Interest Declaration

There are no potential conflicts of interest in this study.

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